

Kernel Level Secure Synchronous (KSS) IPC DESIGN

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Abstract-Inter-process communication (IPC) refers to the exchange of information between processes on a single system or over a network. Many methods exist for communicating between processes on the Linux operating system. The various forms of IPC vary by purpose, such as for synchronization or for passing data and each type of IPC has its merits as well as its drawbacks, typically described in terms of bandwidth and latency. A key feature of KSS is the use of the semaphore interface to support distributed synchronization. The implementation is done at the Linux kernel level to reduce the overhead induced by the strict consistency model. This paper explores the security functionality that the underlying operating system must support to facilitate secure communication between processes in a Linux operating system. UNIX stream sockets, like all session-oriented protocols that provide reliable delivery of data, must be bidirectional. While Linux access controls are sufficiently fine-grained to enforce unidirectionality, it would render the socket connection unusable. As such, there are very few limits on the bandwidth of the back channel introduced - since each participant will need read/write access to the socket, process B could send arbitrary amounts of data back to A, not just the data used to ensure delivery. Stream or session-oriented sockets present additional security complexities that must be included in the evaluation of the architecture. The back channels described above are difficult to exploit, are low bandwidth aside from the file back channels, and, depending on the threat model, might not present a significant attack vector.

Keywords- Distributed Shared Memory (DSM), interprocess communication (IPC),PID process id, operating systems, Synchronous, thread

INTRODUCTION

This thesis introduces a new approach to building an interprocess communication (IPC) library for distributed applications consisting of a distributed shared memory (DSM) subsystem and a distributed semaphores subsystem. The paper begins with a general discussion of the security requirements that must be met by any access control system infrastructure to facilitate secure IPC. The *potential* security benefit of high-performance IPC is straightforward. In contrast to asynchronous or buffering IPC designs the latency of thread-migrating IPC is low enough that applications can be factored into multiple protection domains, each encapsulated by a process boundary and selectively linked by protected, IPC-based **communication**. When a synchronous **communication** mechanism is introduced, the security and trust implications of sender blocking must be considered. When the system design also incorporates user-level pagers, interactions between these pagers, string transfers, and blocking must also be considered. Relatively experienced IPC designers have failed to recognize the potential security issues inherent in this combination. In today's computing world, interprocess communication (IPC) has become an important programming tool. It is no longer conceivable to build significant programs that do not interact with each other, or do not make use of information stored on a remote computer

2. The KSS approach

One of the main issues considered during the designing phase of the KSS system was maintaining the semantics of parallel programs when porting them to a distributed environment. This led to the adoption of System V IPC API as the interface for the KSS system and further enforced the use of a sequential consistency model in preserving consistency of the objects stored by the system. Another important design decision was to implement the system as a kernel module and fully integrate it with the Linux kernel.

1 .name servers KSS name servers have a functionality very similar to that of network name server: naming resolution.

2: kernel modules The architecture of the KSS modules and their interaction is presented in Figure 5.2. The KSS daemon provides the interface between the kernel and the other KSS modules located on remote machines. When inserted in the kernel, it starts a listening thread, a supervising thread, a pool of server threads and a pool of client threads. The functionality of each is described below. The KSS module is hooked into the kernel System V API system calls. See Appendix D for details on how this is done at the kernel level.

3.Security Attributes of Common IPC

Some of the most common include pipes, UNIX domain sockets, shared memory, and message queues. The following sections elaborate on the security benefits and drawbacks to each of these mechanisms.

3.1 Pipes

Pipes, or FIFOs, provide an easy way to send data between processes using the familiar read and write operations. Even if Linux policy is used to ensure the directionality of a FIFO, there is still the possibility of a timing back channel. If the FIFO uses the default blocking mode, a write operation will block until it succeeds. This blocking operation can be combined with the passing of a specific amount of time and thus used to transmit data through a limited bandwidth

3.2 UNIX Domain Sockets

UNIX domain sockets are very simple; each application participating in the IPC creates an endpoint, or a socket, of one of two types. The two types are stream, or session-oriented sockets, and datagram, or session less sockets. There are no revocation issues with domain

sockets and the permissions do not migrate. Migration occurs when the enforcement of a security decision moves from the security sever to another location. Any changes in policy that alter the permissions on the socket files or the socket pipeline will be enforced at the next access. UNIX stream sockets, like all session-oriented protocols that provide reliable delivery of data, must be bidirectional. While Linux access controls are sufficiently fine grained to enforce unidirectionality, it would render the socket connection unusable. Stream or session-oriented sockets present additional security complexities that must be included in the evaluation of the architecture. The back channels described above are difficult to exploit, are low bandwidth aside from the file back channels, and, depending on the threat model, might not present a significant attack vector.

3.3. Shared Memory

Most forms of IPC require the kernel to transfer data through kernel space, which adds overhead and latency. Shared memory has the benefit of not having to go through kernel space - it can be shared between processes entirely in user space. Access controls on shared memory in Linux are fine-grained but non-revocable. A process must have permission to create the shared memory and then permission to attach it to the process' address space. When the segment is attached, another access check is performed based on the type of mapping: read or write. While any process allowed to write to a shared memory segment must also be allowed to read the segment, a process can be granted read only access.

3.4 Message Queue

Message queues are a means of IPC often used to send control information, as opposed to large data sets. They are priority based (or can be treated as such) linked lists used to send records between processes. They are persistent across process termination due to the manner in which the kernel stores them.

This means that one process can create the message and terminate; a second process can start and send a message then terminate; and finally a third process can start, read the message, and finally destroy the message queue. This is a complex case but illustrates a possible way to communicate using message queues.

The message queue structure carries information about the last time a message was read and what process ID (PID) read the message. This could feasibly represent a back channel, but as long as process A cannot read the attributes of the message queue this back channel is prevented. SELinux can prevent process A from reading the attributes and thus eliminate this possible back channel.

4. SYNCHRONOUS IPC

Basic synchronous IPC has the following semantics:

Reliability: The source blocks until the IPC is delivered to the destination or an error occurs.

Error Handling: The source receives an error if the IPC is not delivered to a destination. The destination also receives an error if it is not able to properly receive an IPC.

Timeout Expiration: An IPC is terminated if a destination takes longer than a source timeout to commence receiving an IPC. Similarly, an IPC is also terminated if a source takes longer than a destination timeout to commence sending an IPC.

First, synchronous IPC is reliable, such that an IPC is not complete until it is received by a destination. Thus, the source is blocked until it is known that the IPC was received by the destination. In current systems, the source is unblocked when the IPC is received by the monitor, not the destination, so communication is unreliable by default.

Second, synchronous IPC semantics mean that an error is signaled if the IPC is not delivered to a destination. The source is always signaled. The destination is signaled if it is waiting for an IPC precisely from this source. It must be possible to express a variety of error codes to the source and/or destination. In current systems, once an IPC is delivered to the monitor, the source will not receive a delivery error message.

Third, both the source and destination may set timeouts. These timeouts indicate the amount of time that the source is willing to wait for the destination to commence receipt of an IPC or for a source to commence sending an IPC, respectively.

5. IMPLEMENTATION OF KSS MECHANISM

Overview: Using System V IPC as the API of the system requires the use of the same consistency model provided by System V IPC for parallel programs. There are two obvious approaches to implementing sequential consistency, as follows:

- Keep replicated copies of the shared objects and use a total order communication protocol to enforce an order on accesses to replicated copies of the same shared object
- Maintain a single active copy of the shared object, which is passed around as access to it is requested.

KSS use 2nd approach.

System V IPC API is currently present in the Linux operating system as a set of user-level system calls. The KSS system makes use of the same interface as the System V API and is implemented as a set of kernel modules that are hooked to the System V IPC system calls. KSS could have also been implemented as a user-level system, with minimal kernel modifications. While this second approach was more appealing from the implementation point of view, since it involved less interaction with the kernel, it also suffered from performance penalty due to the large number of context switches between kernel and user space at each system call. A series of benchmarks and tests (presented in Appendix C) proved the advantages of having a kernel level implementation. In this respect, KSSIPC is different from most of the other IPC systems (especially distributed shared memory systems) that are implemented as user-level applications. As implementing KSSIPC as set of kernel modules can help compensate for the use of a strict consistency model.

The overview of the KSSIPC system is presented in Figure 5.1. KSSIPC is composed of a set of KSSIPC Name-Servers and a set of kernel modules local to each node. The name servers handle the distributed key resolution, and keep track of where different System V keys were requested. A set of kernel modules, depicted by KSSIPC blocks in the figure, interact with the kernel and the data structures associated with the virtual memory system to maintain consistency of the shared memory segments. The modules also handle the inter-node interaction through a communication layer defined by a kernel level communication library (see Appendix B). By design, the KSSIPC system is modularized and its interference with the Linux kernel and the kernel data structure is limited.

6. Implementation

6.1 KSSIPC name servers

KSSIPC name servers have a functionality very similar to that of network name server: naming resolution. Whenever a distributed key is used on a node in the system, the node interacts with the name servers to find out if the key has been previously used and which are the nodes that have previously used it. Table 5.1 explains the meaning of messages exchanged between the name server and remote Client(see 5.1.2.4) threads and provides a view of the possible interactions between these entities.

Overview of KSS system

6.1 KSSIPC kernel modules

The architecture of the KSSIPC modules and their interaction is presented in The KSSIPC daemon provides the interface between the kernel and the other KSSIPC modules located on remote machines. When inserted in the kernel, it starts a listening thread, a supervising thread, a pool of server threads and a pool of client threads. The functionality of each is described below. The KSSIPC module is hooked into the kernel System V API system calls.

6.2 The Listener

The listening thread waits for incoming connections from remote KSSIPC client threads. Whenever a new connection is observed the information about the connection is saved in a *connections* list, and the supervisor thread is notified .

The listening thread acts as a gateway between remote machines and the local processing threads.

6.5 The Supervisor

The supervisor thread manages the connections list created by the listener. When data becomes available on any of the connections it moves the connection to an *active connections* list and notifies one of the server threads that information needs to be processed. Although not very intuitive, the separation between the functionality of the Listener thread and the Supervisor thread is very clear.

The Listener thread reacts to incoming connections from remote client threads, while the Supervisor thread reacts to incoming messages (requests) on the already established connections.

6.3 The Server

The server threads, along with the client threads, are the core of the interface between the local KSSIPC modules and remote KSSIPC kernel modules. The server threads process information sent by remote client threads. The messages processed by the server threads are described. Server threads also interact with the kernel data structures in order to provide the information requested by remote clients.

Since the current implementation of the KSSIPC keeps only one active copy of each shared object (shared memory segment or semaphore set), nodes that need to access these objects have to retrieve them from remote location. The server thread has to respond to such requests initiated by remote clients and, when sending the shared object, it has to make sure that the local data structures are in a consistent state so that subsequent local accesses to the object are handled properly and do not generate unexpected faults at the process or the kernel level.

6.4 The Client

Client threads are the entities that request shared objects from remote locations, to allow local processes to access them. Clients become active when a memory page or a semaphore set is accessed by a user space process and is not currently present on the local machine. The kernel identifies the shared object and the key associated with it and wakes up one of the client threads.

The client thread requests the needed information either from a KSSIPC name-server (in case of a new segment allocation) or from a remote KSSIPC server thread (in case a previously defined shared memory page or semaphore set are accessed).

References:

1. Stephan Russel;Besser dept. of computer science ,single user capabilities of IPC University of Sydney Australia 2006
2. Cristian Tapus; In partial fulfillments of requirements, California University, pasadona, California, 2004.
3. J. Benett ,J.Carter and W Zwanepoele .Implementation and performance of munin.ACM presss october, 1991.

7: Conclusions :

Many methods exist for communicating between processes on the Linux operating system. The various forms of IPC vary by purpose, such as for synchronization or for passing data and each type of IPC has its merits.

This paper presented a distributed shared memory system supporting the System V IPC API. In our system, the compiler and kernel cooperate to provide a simple DSM programming model. Another important KSS designed to implement the system as a kernel module and fully integrate it with the Linux kernel. Future research avenues also include the use of speculations and process migration to improve the performance of the KSS system.